

Leadership Style and Person-Environment Fit (Pe Fit) to Improve Innovative Performance through High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs) in Pt Varia Usaha Beton Employees

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ABSTRACT: In the era of globalization and competition increasing business strict, innovation has become the key to maintaining Power and competitive organization. Behavior innovation in something organization becomes a necessary factor in getting attention and being a priority to achieve success in the competitive business world. Study This study influences *Leadership Style* and *Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit)* To increase *Innovative Performance* through *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* for PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. A survey was conducted with a spread questionnaire with the help of *Google Forms* to all over employees totaling 144 employees. Research results state that there exists an influence significance between *Leadership Style* and *PE fit* to *HIHRMPs*, as well exists an influence significance between *Leadership Style* and *PE fit* to *Innovative Performance* and also existence influence significance between *HIHRMPs* to *Innovative Performance*. Companies can make an environment conducive to work for employees who have the creativity to create new solutions and perform innovatively.

KEYWORDS: Leadership Style, Person-environment Fit (PE Fit), High Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs), Innovative Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization and competition increasing business strict, innovation become the key to maintaining Power and competitive organization. Innovation is not only limited to the development of products or technology, but also includes various aspects such as business processes, marketing strategies, and organizational models.

Organizations must be capable of innovating with their superiority competitive in operating their efforts to get to win competition. Behavior innovation in something organization becomes a necessary factor in getting attention and being a priority to achieve success in the competitive business world. This matter started from creativity which is the ability of somebody To produce something new (result development), yes in the form of an idea or real ones that haven't Once There is. The process of realizing or implementing an idea or existing ideas _ There is or idea or idea new that's the next one called behavior innovative. Supportive organization _ innovation and encouragement of employees to contribute with ideas or ideas new will grow and develop performance innovation between employees in a dynamic market.

Innovation Performance can formed from the development of supported skills _ with the utilization of digital technology and knowledge Lots employees (Estensoro et al., 2021). Somebody will capable own performance if he feels suitable and available suitability with the environment in it works. That matter is also called *Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit)*. The writer uses the *Person-environment Fit theory* as knife analysis and as a base for election variables used.

This theory was first time used in psychology organizational and social (Lauver and Kristof-Brown, 2001; Cable and DeRue, 2002) However now also implemented in study management (Seong et al., 2015). The assumption fundamental from *Person-environment Fit (PE Fit) theory* is that enhancement suitability between aspect personal and elemental environment will produce results more work _ Good. Individuals interact with the environment in several dimensions of *Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit)*, such as *Person-Organization (PO) fit*, *Person-Group (PG) fit*, and *Person-Job (PJ) fit* (Lauver and Kristof-Brown, 2001; Jansen and Kristof-Brown, 2006; Yu, 2016).

Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit) refers to suitability between characteristics of individuals with demands or values organization place they Work. Individuals who feel that values and goals organization in line with values and goals personally tend more motivated to innovate.

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Study another conducted by Cahyadi et al (2022) which discusses the influence of Leadership Style, and *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* in improving the individual performance of employees. In research the use of three draft style leadership (*Servant Leadership, Shared Leadership, and Empowering Leadership*).

Based on the theory that has been outlined then for performance innovative individuals will appear or increase if in something organization some leaders have a style capable leadership serving, sharing and empowering employees, as well exists a conducive environment by characteristics employees. The second matter is the furthermore will push employees to follow involved in a way active with ability, knowledge, and motivation to face problem organization. Employees with involvement in the organization will push them to perform innovatively.

The basic idea of *High-Involvement Human Resources Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* is to increase employee motivation by developing their knowledge, skills, and abilities directly towards organizational problems (Rubel et al. 2016). HIHRMPs help employees participate in creating attractive practices in the company (Renkema et al. 2021).

Practice management source Power involving human employees in a way active (*High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices*) plays a role in creating an environment supportive of work innovation. This matter covers giving autonomy to employees, encouraging participation in making decisions, and delivering chances to develop the required skills and competencies for innovation.

Election variable in the study This is based on research conducted by Cahyadi et al (2022) related to *Leadership Styles, High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices, and Individual Employee Performance* as well as research conducted by Goetz and Wald (2021) related to *Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit) and Innovative Performance*. Based on the variables that have been described, then will framework model will be created for conceptual results replication and modification with the use of variable *Leadership Style and Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit) To increase Innovative Performance through High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)*.

The skeleton model conceptual furthermore will tested on employees of PT Varia Usaha Beton in Sidoarjo. As for who became the reason for the model tested on employees of PT Varia Usaha Beton in Sidoarjo is That every year PT Varia Usaha Concrete always stages the *VUB Innovation Award* Where the entire unit is driven F provide creative and innovative ideas in matter increase performance employee.

Importance Understanding how factors like style leadership, conformity individuals with the environment work, and practice management source Power involving human employees in a way active interact for push innovation within the organization become reason main he chose topic study. With understanding relationships and interactions between factors the organization can develop more strategies effective to increase performance innovation.

Study This expectation can give deep insight into How a combination of third factors can influence innovation in organizations, as well as give recommendations for managers and leaders organizations in creating an environment supportive of work innovation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Leadership Style

Leadership style in study This is operationalized as pattern behavior, attitudes, and decisions demonstrated by the leader in managing and influencing member teams To reach an objective organization.

Leader business and HR managers are agents of digital change in the world of work. Leaders This must adopt an effective style of leadership. Cahyadi et al. (2022) in his research use three draft styles of leadership that are:

1. Servant Leadership,
2. Shared Leadership and
3. Empowering Leadership.

Leaders who own a style capable leadership serving, sharing, and empowering employees can influence the performance of their subordinates.

B. Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit)

Person-environment Fit (Pe Fit) in context study This refers to suitability between characteristics individual (skills, values, and preferences) and demands or conditions from environment work that includes culture organization, structure organization, and organizational culture.

Lauver and Kristof-Brown (2001) state that *Person-environment Fit (PE fit)* is the suitability between characteristics of individuals and characteristics of environment work as seen by the individual as important. Individuals interact with the environment in several dimensions, such as:

1. Person-Organization (PO) fit,
2. Person-Group (PG) fit and
3. Person-Job (PJ) fit

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C. High- Involvement Human Resource Management Practices

High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs) in study This refers to practice management source Power man pushing participation active, retrieval decision together, and empowerment employee in the management and development process organization.

Guest (1997) defines *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* as group practice management sources Power purposeful humans to increase performance and engage employees by giving they more Lots autonomy and involvement in making decisions.

According to Huo et al. (2015) as well as Leroy et al. (2018), HIHRMP emerged when employees have developing skills with OK, motivation for implementing it, and the platforms that can used to contribute. Involvement of high employees supports Work HR manager in realizing continuity in something company.

High-involvement human Resource Management Practices that involve employees in a way actively taking decision organization own significant impact on the performance and commitment of employees (Wood & Wall, 2007). According to a study by Cahyadi (2022), *High-Performance Human Resource Management* has 4 (four) indicators:

1. *Human Resource Planning (HRP)*
2. *Training*
3. *Compensation*
4. *Occupational Safety and Health (K3)*

D. Innovative Performance

Innovative Performance in Study This be measured as the ability individual or team To generate new ideas, implement innovation, and contribute to the change or development of products, processes, or practices in the organization.

Robbins (2006) put forward innovation as a process of renewal, and discovery of new ideas, ways, or other. Behavior innovative No appears with so just but behavior innovative moment Work will appear If the employee is faced with challenges in his job and gets broad authority in carrying out duties and responsibilities he answered.

De Jong and Den Hartog (2010) in research say four indicators of behavior innovative Work:

1. *Idea exploration (Exploration of ideas),*
2. *Idea generation (Idea Generation),*
3. *Idea championing (Fighting for Ideas), and*
4. *Idea implementation*

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure. 1 Conceptual Framework

Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then the hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

H1: *Leadership Style* influential positive and significant to *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* for PT Varia Usaha Beton Employees.

H2: *Person-environment Fit* influential positive and significant to *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)* for PT Varia Usaha Beton Employees.

H3: *Leadership Style* Influential Positive and Significant to *Innovative Performance* among PT Varia Usaha Beton Employees.

H4: *Person-environment Fit* influential positive and significant to *Innovative Performance* among PT Varia Usaha Beton Employees.

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H5: High-involvement human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs) influential positive and significant to Innovative Performance among PT Varia Usaha Beton Employees.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

This research implements an explanatory approach that explains the relationship between the four variables measured based on existing theories. The population in this study were employees of PT Varia Usaha Beton. The number of employees working at PT Varia Usaha Beton who were respondents in this research was 144.

The data collection technique was a questionnaire distributed to respondents using Google Forms. This method was adequate for developing information technology for the people in the city. We provided a 5-point Likert scale to classify their answers, namely, strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5).

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)-PLS analysis method using the Smart PLS version 4.0 application which can provide a simultaneous analysis process related to multi-variant research models. Descriptive statistics are used to describe unorganized data and provide an overview of the variables studied.

V. RESULT

A. Respondent Description

Table 1. Respondent Description

Respondent Profile	Description	Fre q	Percentage
Gender	Man	128	88.9
	Woman	16	11.1
	Total	144	100.0
Age	26 to 30 Years	15	10.4
	31 to 35 Years	25	17.4
	36 to 40 Years	17	11.8
	41 to 45 Years	19	13.2
	46 to 50 Years	34	23.6
	Over 50 Years	34	23.6
	Total	144	100.0
last education	JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	1	0.7
	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	35	24.3
	Diploma	29	20.1
	Bachelor	74	51.4
	Postgraduate	5	3.5
	Total	144	100.0
Years of service	Under 5 years old	4	2.8
	5-10 yrs	62	43.1
	Above 10 years	78	54.2
	Total	144	100.0

Table 1 shows that the majority of PT Varia Usaha Beton employees are male, 128 people, or 88.9 percent, 68 people over 45 years old, or 47.2 percent, 74 people, or 51.4 percent have a bachelor's degree. , and had a working period of more than 10 years as many as 78 people or 54.2 percent.

The results of the description of the characteristics of the respondents provide information that in the context of PT Varia Usaha Beton it is still dominated by male employees. The construction and concrete production industry often involves physical work that requires strength and endurance. Ideally, some of these jobs are considered more suitable for male employees. Most employees are also over 45 years old, indicating older age tends to correlate with higher levels of experience. In the construction industry, having employees with extensive experience can help maintain production quality and safety. Older employees also have special skills in project management and problem-solving.

Most of the employees' education is Bachelor's degree. Concrete production processes and construction activities can involve complex technical and managerial aspects. Higher education, at least a bachelor's degree, can provide a deeper understanding of these processes, enabling employees to manage and contribute to the more complex aspects of production and project management. Furthermore, a work period of more than 10 years can show employee stability and loyalty. Employees with longer tenure tend to demonstrate stability in employment and loyalty to the company. In the construction industry, where experience and expertise are highly valued, retaining long-tenured employees can provide a company with a competitive advantage.

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B. Outer Model Analysis Results (Convergent Validity Testing)

Figure. 2 Estimated Results PLS Algorithm

Convergent validity is assessed based on *outer loading* and AVE (*Average Variance Extracted*). The rule of thumb used for convergent validity is *outer loading* ≥ 0.50 and AVE ≥ 0.50 (Hair et al., 2017: 130). Indicators said to be valid can also be assessed from the *T-statistics* value, provided that if the *T-statistics* value is greater than 1.96 or the *p-value* is less than α 5%, then the indicator is said to be valid (Hair et al., 2017: 168).

convergent validity testing showed that all indicators produced an *outer loading* value greater than 0.50, a *T statistics* value greater than 1.96, and a *p-value* less than 0.05, so it was concluded that all indicators met convergent validity and were valid in measuring the construct: leadership style, Person-environment Fit, HIHRMPs, and innovative performance.

C. Results of Inner Model Analysis (Collinearity Analysis)

Collinearity or collinearity is a level of correlation that is too large between independent variables, which causes redundancy of influence so that an influence that should be significant will become insignificant. Collinearity can be measured by the value of the Variance Inflation Factor or VIF. Collinearity is considered high if it has a tolerance value smaller than 0.2 and a VIF value above 5.0 (Hair et al., 2017: 158).

Table. 2 Inner VIF Values

Construct	VIF value against HIHRMPs (Z)	VIF Value of Innovative Performance (Y)
Leadership Style (X1)	1,513	2,221
Person-environment Fit (X2)	1,513	1,749
HIHRMPs (Z)	-	2,422

The results of the analysis of the level of collinearity on the influence path on HIHRMPs, it is known that the VIF value for the leadership style and Person-environment Fit variables produces a value of less than 5, so it is declared free from collinearity. Furthermore, the level of collinearity in the path of influence on innovative performance shows that the VIF value for the variables leadership style, Person-environment Fit, and HIHRMPs also produces a value of less than 5, so it is also declared free from collinearity.

D. Test result Hypothesis

Testing the significance of influence paths between variables according to SmartPLS software was carried out using a bootstrapping approach. The results of hypothesis testing with PLS bootstrapping can be seen in Figure 3.

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Figure. 3 Bootstrapping results PLS

Bootstrapping results produce significance testing for each path. In the 2-tailed test, the research hypothesis can be accepted if the calculated t-value (*T-statistic*) is ≥ 1.96 or the *p-value* is smaller than the error rate (α) of 5%. The following are the path coefficient values (*original sample estimates*), calculated t values (*t-statistics*), and *p values* in the model resulting from PLS Bootstrapping

Table. 3 Hypothesis Test Results

No	Direct Influence	Coeff.	T-Stat	P-Values	Note.
1	Leadership Style (X1) → HIHRMPs (Z)	0.541	7,856	0,000	H ₁ Accepted
2	Person-environment Fit (X2) → HIHRMPs (Z)	0.313	3,926	0,000	H ₂ Accepted
3	Leadership Style (X1) → Innovative Performance (Y)	0.168	2,209	0.028	H ₃ Accepted
4	Person-environment Fit (X2) → Innovative Performance (Y)	0.378	6,107	0,000	H ₄ Accepted
5	HIHRMPs (Z) → Innovative Performance (Y)	0.371	4,582	0,000	H ₅ Accepted

Based on the analysis of the influence between variables, each hypothesis can be explained as follows:

1. Leadership style is influential positive and significant to HIHRMPs

The coefficient value influence of leadership style towards HIHRMPs is 0.541 (positive) with T-statistics of 7.856 (≥ 1.96) and p-value of 0.000 ($\leq 5\%$), so decided influential leadership style is positive and significant to HIHRMPs. Based on the results of this, hypothesis first to state influential leadership style to HIHRMPs on employees still PT Varia Usaha Concrete, yes accepted (H₁ accepted).

Test result hypothesis This gives information that style effective leadership will tend to create environment-supportive work HIHRMPs. Leaders who practice leadership transformational, servant leadership, or style leadership can push the involvement of employees, participation in making decisions, and engagement in practice management source Power more human inclusive.

2. Person-environment Fit matters positively and significantly to HIHRMPs

The coefficient values that influence Person-environment Fit to HIHRMPs are 0.313 (positive) with T-statistics of 3.926 (≥ 1.96) and p-value of 0.000 ($\leq 5\%$), so decided Person-environment Fit also has an influence positive and significant to HIHRMPs. Based on the results this, hypothesis both stated _ Person-environment Fit matters to HIHRMPs on employees still PT Varia Usaha Beton, also be accepted (H₂ accepted).

Test result hypothesis This gives information that suitability between individual and environment Work can increase engagement and performance employee. If employees feel suitable with the culture organization, values, and tasks their work tends more involved in HIHRMPs. Feeling employees that they " fit " with the environment Work can increase motivation and engagement in practice management source Power man.

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3. Leadership style is influential positive and significant to innovative performance

The coefficient value of influence leadership style towards innovative performance is 0.168 (positive) with T-statistics of 2.209 (≥ 1.96) and p-value of 0.028 ($\leq 5\%$), so decided influential leadership style is positive and significant to innovative performance. Based on the results of this, hypothesis the third stated influential leadership style to innovative performance in employees still PT Varia Usaha Beton, also can accept (H 3 accepted).

Test result hypothesis This gives information that the style supportive of leadership innovation, yes stimulates the creativity of employees To create solution new. Leaders who deliver support and acknowledge mark innovation tend to increase performance innovation in employees.

4. Person-environment Fit matters positively and significantly to innovative performance

The coefficient value influence of Person-environment Fit on innovative performance is 0.378 (positive) with T-statistics of 6.107 (≥ 1.96) and a p-value of 0.000 ($\leq 5\%$), so decided Person-environment Fit also has an influence positive and significant to innovative performance. Based on the results of this, hypothesis the fourth stated Person-environment Fit matters to innovative performance in employees still PT Varia Usaha Beton, also can accept (H 4 accepted).

Test result hypothesis This gives information that suitable individuals with environment-supportive work _ innovation can create possible conditions Employees For to develop creative ideas. If employees feel environment Work they support creativity and innovation, they tend to contribute to performance innovation.

5. HIHRMPs are influential positive and significant to innovative performance

The coefficient value influencing HIHRMPs against innovative performance is 0.371 (positive) with T-statistics of 4.582 (≥ 1.96) and p-value 0.000 ($\leq 5\%$), so decided that HIHRMPs also have an impact positive and significant to innovative performance. Based on the results of this, hypothesis the fifth stated HIHRMPs are influential to innovative performance in employees still PT Varia Usaha Beton, also can accept (H 5 accepted).

Test result hypothesis This gives information that practice management source Power involving humans and employees in a way active, encouraging participation, and creating culture can create a supportive environment of innovation. Involvement of employees in the retrieval process decisions, empowerment, and rewards can motivate them to contribute to performance innovation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the problem formulation, literature review, analysis of research results, and discussions described in the previous chapters, the results of this research can be concluded as follows:

1. *Leadership style* influences *HIHRMPs* for PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. Effective leadership style will tend to create environment-supportive work *HIHRMPs*. Leaders who practice leadership transformational, *servant leadership*, or style leadership can push the involvement of employees, participation in making decisions, and engagement in practice management source Power more human inclusive. Research results This supports a study previously carried out by Cahyadi et al. (2022) who also said that *Leadership Style* is influential in *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)*.

2. *Person-environment Fit* matters to *HIHRMPs* for PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. Suitability between individual and environment Work can increase engagement and performance of employees. If employees feel suitable with the culture organization, values, and tasks their work _ tends more involved in *HIHRMPs*. Feeling employees that they " *fit* " with the environment Work can increase motivation and engagement in practice management source Power man. Research results in This support study previously carried out by Saufi et al (2023), Cesario et al (2022), and Boon et al (2011), where completely state the same thing that *Person-environment Fit* influential to *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)*.

3. *Leadership Style* influences *Innovative Performance* among PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. Supportive leadership style innovation, yes stimulate creativity employee For creating solution new. Leaders who deliver support and acknowledge mark innovation tend to increase performance innovation in employees. Research results in This support study previously conducted by Li and Tang (2022), Cui et al (2022), and Khan et al (2020), Where completely state the same thing that *Leadership Style* is influential to *Innovative Performance*.

4. *Person-environment Fit* matters to *Innovative Performance* among PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. Suitable individuals with environment supportive work innovation can create possible conditions _ employee For develop creative ideas. If employees feel environment Work they support creativity and innovation, they tend to contribute to performance innovation. Research results This supports the study previously done by Goetz and Wald (2021) and Zhang et al (2023), Which completely state the same thing that *Person-environment Fit* is influential to *Innovative Performance*.

5. *HIHRMPs* are influential in *Innovative Performance* among PT Varia Usaha Beton employees. Practice management source Power involving humans _ employees in a way active, encouraging participation, and creates a culture inclusive can create a supportive environment _ of innovation. Involvement of employees in the retrieval process decisions, empowerment, and rewards can motivate them to contribute to performance innovation. Research results This support study previously conducted by Kutieshat

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and Farmanesh (2022), Elshaer et al (2023), Renkema et al (2021), Yasir and Majid (2020) as well as Etaan and Jain (2019), where completely state the same thing that *HIHRMPs* are influential to *Innovative Performance*.

SUGGESTIONS

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. The results of this research can be used as input for officials within PT Varia Usaha Beton to pay more attention to Leadership Style, *Person-environment Fit*, and *High-Involvement Human Resource Management Practices (HIHRMPs)*.
2. The results of this research can be used as a source of ideas and input for the development of this research in the future. In further research, it could be considered to add variables that can influence career development, job satisfaction, and performance other than the variables used in this research such as Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture.

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